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Analyzing Teachers' Reported Motives and Students' Perceived Effects of Code-Switching in English Classrooms in Hyderabad

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Abstract

This study has been conducted to investigate teachers' reported reasons for using code-switching in the English classroom, and the benefits and drawbacks perceived by students. This study is qualitative in nature, in which structured interviews were used to collect data, and the data were analyzed through thematic analysis. Purposive sampling was used to select the sample, which consisted of 30 participants. The participants were 15 students and 15 teachers from Hyderabad. The results of this study indicate that most of the teachers prefer code-switching to explain grammatical rules and difficult vocabulary, and some students perceive it as helpful, while others find it concerning. The study recommends a balanced integration of code-switching in the English classroom.

Key words: code-switching, ESL classroom, bilingual education, (L1) support, Hyderabad

Introduction

Code-switching is commonly known as the practice of shifting between two or more languages or simply "changing of two or more languages during ongoing speech when both speakers know and understand these languages" (Cook, 2000:83). Gumperz defined code switching as "the juxtaposition within the same speech exchange of passages of speech belonging to two different grammatical systems or subsystems" (Gumperz, 1982:59). In Pakistani language learning institutes, it has been widely noticed that code-switching is often practiced in classrooms when teaching English as a second language, while mostly students here share same L1, generally Urdu or Sindhi. Though being used largely in language classrooms, its efficiency as a language learning tool has been topic of debate among researchers. Some assert that it is an effective instruction tool, while others argue that it obstructs the focus and proficiency among learners.

Hyderabad is a multilingual city of Pakistan, where students come from diverse linguistic backgrounds, serves students from interior Sindh as well. Here primary languages are Urdu and Sindhi, while English used in educational and official

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sectors. However, it has been found in English language institutes that students that students often lack proficiency in English, so the practice of code-switching is widely noticed in the language classrooms. As students struggle in comprehending entirely English-based lectures, teachers frequently switch between their L1 and English to make the lectures easily understandable. Teachers also opt for code-switching in classrooms because it helps create an inclusive language learning environment and ensures the engagement from the students as well. This research investigates why code-switching is commonly practiced, how it is viewed, and what are the perceived drawbacks associated with its use in English language learning classrooms in Hyderabad.

Though the practice of code-switching has been previously investigated in government schools (Nawaz et al., 2023), and urban educational settings (Murad et al., 2024), along with universities (Ali et al., 2024), least research is done on Hyderabad's private language learning institutions. As bilingualism is common in this region, and English also plays an important role in educational and professional growth, it is crucial to address this contextual gap and find out why code-switching is most preferred pedagogical tool in language learning institutions, and how it influences the English language learning an proficiency. This research answers the following research questions:

- a) What are the main reasons behind English teachers' code switching in private language institutes of Hyderabad?
- b) What benefits do students perceive in teachers' use of code-switching in English language classrooms?
- c) What drawbacks or negative impacts do students associate with teachers' use of code-switching in English language classrooms?

Literature Review

Code-switching refers to switching from one language or dialect to another while speaking (Rodman and Fromkin, 1998). It has been widely observed in bilingual and multilingual contexts, where people speak two or more languages, often switch their languages automatically and unconsciously (Sert, 2005; Jingxia, 2010). Cook (2000) emphasized that for code switching, both languages should be known to speakers.

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Sometimes, to show unity, bilingual and multilingual people use code switching when their cultural background is the same (Skiba, 1997; Sert, 2005), and sometimes Speakers deliberately use code switching in order to influence and explain the situation in a way they want, to express personal and deeper feelings (Trudgill, 2000). To better understand this phenomenon, several scholars have categorized types of code-switching. Three main types of code-switching are: 1) inter-sectional: when sentences are switched. e.g., I am learning English baqi Urdu to mujhy ati h. 2) intra-sentential: refers to changing of two languages within the single sentence. Eg, Let's eat biryani aur raita. 3) tag switching: insertion of tags, phrases, of one language into another. eg, Please, listen na! (Poplack, 2000; Jingxia, 2010). Situational and metaphorical are two additional types of code switching triggered by context that are discussed by Gumperz (1982). Situational code switching refers to switching according to situation and setting. Metaphorical code switching is about expressing emotions.

Code-Switching in ESL Classrooms

In multilingual countries, code switching is common in ESL classrooms when students or teachers switch languages (Lin, 2013). It is used to instruct, explain lessons, and teach grammar in an ESL classroom (Gulzar, 2010). Martin (1999) observed some reasons behind code switching of teachers in classroom:

- a) To give a signal about starting the lesson.
- b) To make a change in tone
- c) To add quick comment
- d) To talk to specific one
- e) To give instructions to students

Additionally, importance of code-switching in ESL classroom has been explained by Jacobson (1983). He addressed five reasons for using code-switching for effective learning. 1) it helps students to learn vocabulary and grammar effectively, because they get input in both languages. 2) Students understand content better. 3) It shows the equality and importance of both languages by using them in the classroom. 4) It helps students to stay focused and learn well. 5) It promotes a free environment and natural language use.

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However, the usefulness of code-switching remains debated, for some researchers, code switching is helpful and beneficial in the ESL context, while others believe that it hinders the learning of a second language and affects its proficiency negatively (Macaro, 2005).

According to Ahmad and Jusoff (2009), code switching is not only useful for teachers, but it also helps students in achieving a good understanding of information and improving communication. It helps in understanding and learning a second language well since students get enough input. Moreover, meaning is cleared; explanations are simplified, so it helps students to stay focused. Since, Krashen (1982) suggested acquiring language naturally, input must be comprehensible. If students do not understand what is being taught about the target language, they will hesitate to perform any task requiring the use of that language. Thus, teachers adopt code-switching, as a method of making learners learn and comprehend adequately (Ellis, 2015). Greggio and Gil (2007) on their part made a supporting statement regarding code switching, citing that it aids in the explanation of grammar rules and vocabulary, and students are able to learn, comprehend, and engage in class sessions. It is useful and advantageous to the individuals who are not high-level learners since it aids them in comprehending lectures and ideas more effectively (Ahmad & Jusoff, 2009; Selamat, 2014). Jacobson (1983) also assumed that code switching is useful since it brings information and application of both languages. Cook (2000) explains that code switching results in an all-encompassing learning atmosphere where learners can commit errors and employ L1 to communicate unreservedly.

Also, Nordin et al. (2013) researched code switching. His study found that code switching has a positive impact on students' English learning. Learners admitted that they learn better when the teacher codeswitches to explain Grammar. Moreover, students' anxiety is reduced, their confidence is built, and they feel more comfortable when the teacher uses code switching. Novianti & Said (2021), Indonesian researchers, did an experimental study to find out how code switching impacts 2nd language learning. Two groups were created; one was allowed to use code switching, while the other was restricted. At the end, students who were allowed to be in a classroom setting where code switching was allowed learned and performed better.

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This study supports the pedagogical use of code-switching, calling it a helpful strategy to reduce anxiety, enhance confidence, and enable students to better target a language. It also improves the relationship between teacher and students and makes the classroom environment relaxed and positive (Moghadam et al, 2012). Similarly, Peregoy and Boyle (2013) also argue that L1 is helpful for both learning and teaching. When L1 is allowed in the classroom, the classroom environment becomes more comfortable because learners are not pressurized to follow an English-only policy. It reduces their anxiety and enhances learners' motivation to participate and confidence.

Criticism of Code-Switching in ESL

However, not all researchers favor code-switching in ESL classrooms. Fillmore (1985), Brown (2007), and Jingxia (2010) state that the interruption of another language in ESL classrooms can hinder students' learning. Students over-rely on their first language; it creates difficulty for them to practice and use English. It can also negatively affect students' long-term progress and performance in a second language, preventing them from actively engaging with English and also reducing their motivation (Chambers, 1991; Halliwell & Jones, 1991). While Sridhar, (1996) says code switching is the sign of weakness, laziness and low expertise in learning and teaching. Similarly, Brown (2006) believes code switching shows poor language skills and a lack of competence. Using it may cause obstruction in English learning and negatively affect students' speaking. The Main Purpose of learning L2 will be lost if L1 is used excessively (Jingxia, 2010). Furthermore, it can also lead to long-term problems. Sometimes when L1 is mostly used in the classroom, students start mixing concepts and rules of both languages, and then students become habitual of using incorrect English without even realizing it (Zhu, 2008). Code-switching can lead to the fossilization of errors. When students make a habit of switching languages, they start using non-standard English, and over time, these mistakes become permanent (Fillmore, 1985; Jingxia, 2010). Krashen (1985) insisted that there should be maximum exposure to the target language in the classroom instead of using L1. Language learning can be affected negatively by over-use of L1 and limited exposure to target language (Novianti & Said, 2021). Students will learn effectively when only the target language is being used around them (Ellis, 2015). To use code-switching as

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a helpful and useful tool in the context of the ESL classroom, Jacobson (1983) suggested some rules to be followed: 1) excessive use of L1 should be prevented. 2) Both languages should be equally distributed (50/50). 3) Code-switching must be natural and unconscious. 4) Only code switching should be used to reach the goal. If one is not following these guidelines, it's instructed code switching affecting students' learning negatively (Jacobson, 1983).

In spite of the vastness of the literature on the advantages and limitations of code-switching, hardly any research has made a focus specifically on private language institutes in Hyderabad, a linguistically heterogeneous city. This localized context of Urdu-English and Sindhi-English bilingualism is unexplored, hence this study attempts to bridge this gap by examining how code-switching is employed and viewed in private English language classrooms in Hyderabad and whether it affects language learning of them.

Methodology

Research Design

According to Creswell (1994), qualitative research is the detailed study of people's experiences, their perspectives. It is conducted in natural setting, involves using words to get in-depth knowledge. As the focus of this research is on how students perceive code switching of teachers; its pros and cons in ESL classroom and why teachers use code switching. So, qualitative method was appropriate to be used in this research to investigate students' as well teachers' point of view regarding code switching and its pros and cons.

Sampling Technique and Participants

To conduct this study, 15 English teachers and 15 English learners were used as a sample and to collect this sample Purposive sampling technique was used, which is a type of non-probability sampling. This approach was chosen because it allows researchers to intentionally select participants who are most relevant to the research objectives. As stated by Gay and Airasian (2000), purposive sampling is like a judgmental sampling in which researcher selects those individuals who are best suited to provide rich, relevant data. Therefore, the sample consisted of total 30 participants from Hyderabad institutes having an experience and exposure to code switching in

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English classroom. This sample seemed suitable and best, since Hyderabad is educational hub for learners coming from different areas of interior Sindh with diverse linguistic backgrounds. In such classroom environments, learners as well as teachers experience code-switching because it becomes common practice. Their direct exposure to code-switching ensured that the data collected would be rich, relevant, and directly aligned with the study's focus on code-switching in ESL classrooms.

Data Collection Tool

To collect data, structured interviews were used as a data collection tool. These are preplanned interviews in which all questions are designed and decided in advance before conducting interview. As Denscombe (2009, p. 232) states, interview is the best and highly effective tool to get detailed responses on specific topic. The motive of the conducting interviews was to get to know about both teachers' and students' point of views and experiences regarding code switching in English classroom.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were taken seriously. Taking consent and protecting respondents' anonymity are two suggested ways of ensuring ethical consideration (Creswell, 2012). Hence, after students' and teachers' consent, interviews were conducted. Before starting interview, they were assured that they would remain anonymous, their names, their identities and personal information will remain confidential and will not be shared without their permission. Additionally, their participation was voluntary, they could participate if they want and could leave any time without providing a reason.

Data Analysis Tool

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data, which is one of the most common methods used to analyze the collected data (through interviews) in qualitative research. It is subjective in nature allowing researchers to analyze, interpret, and make sense of data personally. It is about pointing out main ideas of collected data, and generating multiple themes of repeated concepts to make it clear what is said and what message is conveyed. To conduct thematic analysis, researchers follow different ways and steps. However, in this study six-step framework to conduct thematic analysis

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introduced by Braun & Clarke (2006) was followed, which includes following six steps: (1) familiarizing with the data, (2) generating codes, (3) looking for common themes, (4) reviewing themes, (5) defining and naming themes, and (6) producing the report. This method enabled the researchers understand common ideas and experiences of individuals about code-switching in ESL classrooms.

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Data Analysis and Findings

Reasons Behind Teachers' Code-Switching in English Classroom

The first objective of the research was to identify the reasons behind the instructors using code-switching from English to other regional languages like from English to Urdu or English to Sindhi, during their lectures in classroom. The analysis of their responses showed that most of them agreed that the main reason behind code-switching to simplify the complex ideas or the lesson contents for the learners in easier way. As many teachers stated that learners often get confused and puzzled if they are taught fully in English. In such cases, they believe that switching in their native or regional language helped the learners to understand the lessons contents more easily and efficiently. As T3 mentioned, *"Because students' native language is not English, so they understand the content better when explained in their 1st language"*, while T11 reported, *"I code-switch whenever, my students are unable to understand whatever I am teaching them."* This highlights that teachers use code switching to enhance clarity and ensure effective understanding.

Teachers also mentioned that they practice code-switching while defining difficult vocabulary, abstract ideas, especially during explanation of literature, grammar rules, or discussing tricky concepts like moral dilemmas or social issues. One of the main reasons of code-switching was grammar instruction. As explained by T7, *"Teaching English grammar can be hard sometimes. One needs to give examples from L1 to explain the concepts better."* While T2 highlighted need of code switching to explain grammatical structures, stating, *"Teaching any grammar topic is the hardest part in which students often get confused, so it is required to switch in L1 to make them understand the rules properly. For example, Subject + verb + Object – 'Ali plays in the park' becomes 'Ali park main khelta hai'."* Similarly, T9 stated, *"I use code switching to explain Grammar uses, sentence structures, etc."* highlighting grammar instruction as one of the main cited area for code-switching.

On the other hand, some teachers clearly reported using code switching for vocabulary clarification, such as T5 admitted, *"To explain difficult words and meaning ,I practice code-switching,"* while T13 stated, *"I use code-switching when I have to teach my students new vocabulary, grammar, and some tasks."* And T3 also

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shared that *“once teaching Shakespeare’s sonnet summary, there were certain words that students found hard to understand. So I used code-switching to explain those words in Urdu, so that they can understand the meaning easily.”* These responses make it clear that code-switching plays a major role in making grammar and vocabulary easy to understand, especially for low proficient students.

Some stated that they employ code-switching when they find learners absent-minded or hesitant, especially in beginning of the session where learners lack foundational knowledge of the subject. In such manner, code-switching serves as a link between the learners’ prior knowledge and the new concept being introduced. As T6 explained, *“When I’m teaching a novel and encounter any culturally unfamiliar concept or idiom, I switch from English to Urdu or Sindhi as to make it relatable for the learners. It instantly enhances their engagement and understanding.”* T2 commented, *“Learners come from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds and not all of them possess the same level of English understanding. So, in this situation code-switching helps me reach out to everyone equally.”*

Code-Switching as a Classroom Approach

Through data, it was found that teachers do not only perceive code-switching as a language tool but as a teaching approach as well. They commented that switching between English and their L1 helped them effectively manage the classroom. For example, when learners became chaotic or distracted, switching to Urdu or Sindhi often led to refocusing their attention promptly. As T14 explained, *“Yes, when students are out of control and are not listening in L2 then I switch to the L1, which is more familiar to them, so that they may get attentive and listen to the teacher.”* Teachers also noted that learners felt more connected and responded emotionally or respectfully when handled in their mother tongue, especially when trying to maintain discipline or motivation in the classroom. *“Using mother tongue is the best way to make someday emotional, motivated, or whatever you want them.”*

Code-switching was also used while giving instructions, explaining assignments, and/ or giving feedback. T8 reported, *“I did code switching to explain students their assignment. I tried it in English first but many of them were still confused. So, I code switch to clarify.”* T2 shared, *“If I explain homework in English*

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only, most students keep asking again and again. But if I shift to Sindhi, they understand quickly, and I don't have to repeat so much."

Teachers shared that teaching lesson contents fully in English often led to confusion or repeated queries from students. As admitted by T7 and T13, *"Recently, I practiced code-switching in my class to describe a fictional story from their textbook which had difficult vocabulary, so that they may understand and enjoy it effectively without being confused or distracted from it. And it worked, they thoroughly enjoyed it and were hooked till the end, asking for the meanings of difficult words."*, *"Yesterday, I was teaching Shakespeare sonnet summary there was some words difficult to understand but when I did code switching student easily got the concept."* So, switching to the native language helped to ensure the clarity and saved time as well. Likewise, while explaining students their points of weakness and areas where they needed to improve, teachers switched to L1 to ensure that students properly grasp the feedback.

These responses indicated that teachers do not practice code-switching for only one purpose of explaining difficult concepts, but to grasp students attention, to instruct them, to create discipline in classroom, and to offer feedback.

Teachers' Prospect on the Efficiency of Code-Switching

Most of the teachers were found inclined towards the practice of code-switching in language learning classrooms in Hyderabad. According to them it is a practical and effective teaching tool in linguistically diverse regions like Hyderabad, as it creates an inclusive learning environment, ensuring that no learner may feel left behind. They mentioned that, it also serves to boost the confidence among shy students to interact in English. T13 mentioned, *"when I use code-switching, students understand better and try to participate confidently"*.

However, some teachers reported concerns about the overuse of code-switching. They believed that too much reliance on the native language can impede the students' proficiency in English. As T9 stated, *"There should be a balance. If we frequently translate everything, learners will stop trying to comprehend English independently."* T12 commented, *"Code-switching is helpful, however it must be lessened gradually as to improve learners' language skills. Or else, it would become a habit."*

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How Students Benefit from Teachers' Use of Code-Switching

The second objective of the research was to explore learners' views on the use of code-switching in their English classrooms. Most of the learners had a positive response on their teachers' usage of code-switching. They believed it simplified the learning for them, especially the grammar rules, difficult vocabulary, or abstract concepts like humility, self-awareness, and cultural ideas. As S12 responded, "*I understand grammar rules better when they are explained in Urdu.*" While S1 mentioned, "*Teacher explains hard words in Urdu or Sindhi, and then we understand the meaning.*" And S5 cleared, "*Code-switching helps students to understand difficult concepts into simple terms by using native or regional language.*"

Many students agreed that when their teachers practice code-switching while teaching, they feel less anxious or stressed and find themselves comparatively more comfortable and engaging in the class. They were more confident in asking queries and giving responses. S7 shared, "*When the teacher teaches in both English and Urdu, I don't feel hesitant anymore before asking any question. As I know I can ask anything and I won't be judged.*" Similarly, S9 noted, "*Yes, it does reduce my anxiety and I feel comfortable.*"

Moreover, some students also pointed out that teachers' code switching enhances their participation and minimize their fear of making mistakes while speaking English. As stated by S10, "*when teacher himself switch languages, it makes me less scared to speak*". Similarly, S11 mentioned, "*I start participating in activities, and also asking questions*". Learners also felt that code-switching has helped design an inclusive and supportive environment of the class, especially for the students who struggle with English. This language approach helped them feel connected to the lesson contents effectively and allowed them to go along with the class more easily.

Overall, these responses show that students perceive code-switching of teacher as a supportive tool enhancing their understanding of content, grammar, vocabulary, alongside participation and confidence.

Students' Concerns on the Drawbacks

While many students acknowledged the advantages of code-switching, some also raised concerns regarding it, which is the third objective of the study as well. A huge

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number of them felt that overuse of Urdu or Sindhi in English classes limited their exposure to English, which could negatively impact their fluency and confidence. S13 shared, *"Definitely it does affect my speaking fluency. Because, I keep listening my teacher using my native language, we participate in native language so it leads to lack of practice of speaking English."* similarly, another participant S2 addressed, *"Yes, I think it does decrease the level of fluency in English as we are not solely exposed to English but with the mixture of our own language which lessens the confidence in speaking in English."*

Furthermore, they believed that if teachers frequently switched to the native language, learners would not be able to develop the habit of thinking in English or forming sentences independently. According to S6, *"Since only Sindhi/Urdu is being heard, so mind becomes habitual of thinking in that language."* While, S15 responded, *"when there is little exposure to English language, it affects my ability to think in English language."*

Some learners shared that code-switching can make them over-dependent on translations, leading them to comprehend English indirectly rather than understanding it directly in their minds. S1 responded, *"Yes, when teacher only use L1 to explain Grammar, words, sentence meaning etc. It's like he is teaching us how to translate rather than how to use English effectively."*

This dependence on code-switching kills students' curiosity to learn English their, and limits their motivation to practice English actively. S7 stated, *"At first it helps, but if it persists for too long, we become lazy. We wait for the teacher to translate for us from English to L1 instead of trying to comprehend it on our own."* Another participant S10 said, *"When the teacher uses excessive Sindhi in the class, I feel there is no need to practice English anymore."*

These responses highlight that students perceive teachers' code switching as a barrier, limiting their practice, affecting fluency, making them unable to think in English alongside habitual of translating.

Preferred Language Classroom Approach

Learners gave mixed responses when they were asked about the type of classroom setting they preferred, entirely English or should have code-switching. Many shared

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that a mixed approach is more effective, especially for the beginners. They appreciated that starting with a blend of English and L1 helped them comprehend better and engage more confidently. Although, they also mentioned the need to expand English exposure gradually with time. While, few advanced learners and more confident students believed that entirely English based classrooms would be more favourable in the long term. They felt that it would motivate students to think and speak more fluently in English and would lessen the over reliance on native language. These learners saw the need for creating an engaging English environment for the effective learning outcomes.

Overall, on the basis of analysis of the responses from both teachers and students, the subsequent key findings emerged. Code-switching is frequently used by English teachers in private institutes, in Hyderabad. Addressing the first objective, it was reported by teachers that they opt to use code-switching to explain the meaning of new vocabulary, abstract and complex ideas, sentence structure, grammar. handle students, or support them emotionally. Teachers perceive it as a helpful teaching approach, especially for less proficient learners and in multilingual classroom settings. They feel it produces a comfortable learning environment and ensures the throw out involvement of students. Some of the teachers viewed code switching as a helpful tool leading to a relaxed atmosphere in the classroom. While, according to other teachers, by using code switching it is easy to maintain classroom discipline, and make students focused on lessons.

The second objective of the study was to explore students' perceptions of positive impacts of code switching. Responses of students showed that students see code switching impacting positively. Students perceived teachers' code switching positively, stating that it helps them in reducing anxiety and increasing participation. They also believed that they learn better when teachers use code switching. Moreover, learning new vocabulary and grammar rules in the target language might be challenging, since teachers' code switching help students understand well.

Regarding the third objective about negative impacts, study uncovered students' concerns about excessive use of code-switching. Students pointed out that teachers' overuse of code-switching affects their fluency in speaking and limit

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learners' motivation to practice English actively. Additionally, code switching has made them dependent on translations instead of learning and using English directly. Some of the students also think that there is a need of a proper exposure to English, to improve proficiency in English language. Both the groups preferred the practice of code-switching as a temporary bridging approach to support students' proficiency and confidence, which may be reduced gradually as soon as desired results become evident. As code switching is preferred approach among students and teachers in Hyderabad, there should be a balanced integration of it to make learners more confident and proficient in English.

Discussion

The findings of this study explored why code switching is used by teachers, and how it is perceived by learners in institutes of Hyderabad. It is uncovered that code-switching is not used unintentionally or unconsciously as a linguistic habit of teachers, but it is used purposefully. For teachers, code-switching is a pedagogical strategy that facilitates students' understanding of content better, and it also helps manage the classroom. Similarly, Jacobson (1983) pointed out in his study that students learn and understand the content better when the teacher uses code switching. Ellis (2015) mentioned in the findings of his study that teachers opt to switch code to enable students to learn and understand effectively. Moreover, in this study it was assumed by teachers that their code-switching enhances classroom engagement and participation. This was also evident in students' responses, where many reported that they paid more attention when teachers switched to Urdu or Sindhi, especially during classroom management or when instructions were unclear.

The first objective of this study was to explore the reasons why teachers use code-switching. Results showed that most of the teachers prefer code switching to explain grammatical rules and difficult vocabulary. This aligns with the study of Greaggio and Gill (2007), who stated that code-switching helps in the explanation of grammar and vocabulary. Similarly, Gulzar (2010) also mentioned that code-switching is used as a tool to teach grammar in the ESL classroom. Findings reveal that it was assumed by teachers that their code-switching enhances classroom engagement and participation. As Novianti & Said (2021) stated, students' anxiety is

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reduced and their motivation to participate is increased. Moreover, teachers expressed that switching to students' L1 while giving instructions and feedback not only ensured clarity but also saved time and helped avoid misunderstandings. They also viewed it as a respectful and emotional connection with students, especially in maintaining discipline.

The second objective was about exploring benefits of teachers' code-switching, perceived by students. Students viewed code switching positively. For them, code switching made learning easier. It helped them understand grammar, vocabulary, and especially difficult concepts. Some of them accept that they become less anxious and do not hesitate to ask questions if the teacher applies code-switching. This supports the idea of Nordin et al. (2013) and Novianti & Said (2021), who also believed that code switching is a helpful tool to reduce anxiety among students, enhance their confidence, and motivation to participate. It was also mentioned that code-switching is useful for low proficient learners, because they understand better what the teacher explains. This perspective aligns with Krashen's (1982) input hypothesis theory that comprehensible input plays the main role in effective learning. However, not all students were in favor of teachers' code-switching. A few students shared that code switching was especially helpful when they were new to English learning, and they appreciated the occasional translation of assignment instructions or difficult vocabulary into their L1.

The third objective of this study was to explore students' perspectives on the drawbacks of code switching in the classroom. Students felt that the use of Urdu and Sindhi in the English classroom affects their fluency and reduces practice. They believed that code switching had made them habitual to translations, instead of using English directly. Limited exposure to English affects their learning and performance. As Krashen (1985) insisted, there must be maximum exposure to the target language in the classroom to learn a language effectively. These findings also relate to the study of Novianti & Said (2021), who stated that over-reliance on the first language and limited exposure to the target language in the classroom could negatively affect language learning, and Ellis (2015), who noted students will learn more effectively when only the target language is being used around them. Students as well as teachers

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agreed that code switching is a useful and helpful strategy when it is not used in the wrong way. This was supported by many students who mentioned that too much use of Urdu or Sindhi limited their chance to practice English, making them feel less confident in real-life situations where only English is used.

This study explored that code-switching should be used when students are beginners with low proficiency, and reduced when they improve and become proficient. This relates with Jacobson's (1983) suggestions about use of code-switching. He suggested not to use code switching excessively in the classroom; there should be a balance, and code switching should be used to reach a particular goal. Several teachers also recommended gradually reducing code switching as students gain confidence and begin responding in English more frequently.

For an ideal language policy in the classroom, learners had mixed opinions. Some of the students favored code switching at the beginner level, while others preferred an English-only class to improve fluency. Therefore, code switching has to be practiced strategically to support learning and understanding only without inducing dependency. In Hyderabad, typically students' L1 is Sindhi or Urdu, and English is their second or foreign language. In the private institutes of Hyderabad, students come from different backgrounds, and their English proficiency also varies. Hence, code switching as a supportive scaffold is justified, making lessons easier and clearer. However, students and teachers think that the overuse of regional languages can negatively affect fluency. They prefer maximum exposure to English in the classroom to learn effectively. Therefore, the study concludes that while code switching has strategic value, it must be balanced with immersion in English to help learners become confident, independent users of the language.

However, despite contributions, this study is not without certain limitations. Firstly, the sample size was short including only 30 participants (15 teachers and 15 pupils), which is unable to accurately represent the broader population of English-language learners and teachers in Hyderabad or elsewhere. Secondly, data were collected and relied only on structured interviews. While these provided transparent responses, using only a single method could have been restrictive of the depth and diversity of information. Lastly, the research focused only on urban private

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institutes in Hyderabad, excluding rural settings and government schools, so the findings cannot be generalized to those contexts. Finally, as a qualitative study, the results offer contextual understanding rather than universal conclusions. Future research could involve larger and more diverse samples, combine multiple data collection tools, and include classroom observations to support deeper analysis.

Conclusion

This qualitative study inquired the role of code-switching in Hyderabad-based English language institutes, by getting teachers' prospect on its preferred usage, along with students' outlook relevant to its influence; both positive plus negative. Collected data from both the groups, it found that code-switching is a most common and repeated yet purposeful practice to assist language learning, especially in multilingual regions.

Teachers mentioned their views that how code-switching help them grasping students' focus, maintaining discipline in class, explain complex topics and hard vocabulary and teach grammar rules to students easily. They do not intend to replace English with the native language but to use it to ensure their understanding and participation. They also reported that code-switching assist them in engaging with students in better way. Furthermore, students' views are also positive at some point, as they stated that code-switching practice by their teachers, helped lessen their anxiety, and made them comfortable in participating in the classroom with confidence. Though, they also believed that over reliance on code-switching may limit their proficiency and proficiency in English.

Hence, the study summarizes that code-switching can be an effectual learning strategy in English language institutes. However, it is recommended to follow a balanced approach, by gradually limiting code-switching as learners gain confidence in English, to ensure increased understanding and language development. Hence, this research emphasize the significance of context-based teaching strategies in language learning classrooms and recommend future researchers to explore long-term effects of code-switching on learners' proficiency and independent language use.

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